

Modeling and Optimization of Aggregate Production Planning - A Genetic Algorithm Approach

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Abstract—The Aggregate Production Plan (APP) is a schedule of the organization's overall operations over a planning horizon to satisfy demand while minimizing costs. It is the baseline for any further planning and formulating the master production scheduling, resources, capacity and raw material planning. This paper presents a methodology to model the Aggregate Production Planning problem, which is combinatorial in nature, when optimized with Genetic Algorithms. This is done considering a multitude of constraints of contradictory nature and the optimization criterion – overall cost, made up of costs with production, work force, inventory, and subcontracting. A case study of substantial size, used to develop the model, is presented, along with the genetic operators.

Keywords—Aggregate Production Planning, Costs, and Optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

AGGREGATE Production Plans (APP) concern about the allocation of resources of the company to meet the demand forecast. Optimizing the APP problem implies minimizing the cost over a finite planning horizon. This can be done by adjusting production load as well as inventory and employment levels over a certain period of time to achieve the lowest cost while satisfying demand and considering the specific constraints for each particular case (company dependent). A good APP has the capacity to positively influence the bottom line and also permit a long-term view of the organization performance. This avoids having to make short-term decisions and fire-fight problems, adversely affecting the organization's long term perspective [1].

Managers have access to the break-down monthly or weekly demand forecast for the next planning horizon,

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normally 1 year. In practice, managers capitalize on the forecasted demand to achieve long-run profitability. They face major constraints in the number of workers, facilities and plant capacity to fulfill the demand. Therefore, not only all the demand must be met in each planning period (month/week), but costs have to be minimized. Managers may decide if meeting market demand results in lower long-term profit, to backorder and/or ask the subcontractors to do a part of the products. The APP problem deals with how to employ the available workforce, resources and facilities, including external contractors, to best satisfy the demand which is defined through APP [1].

Although a number of production planning approaches have been developed in order to improve planning automation and increase efficiency of production planning [2], but a lot of problems in the area of production planning are subject to highly complex constraints which make them very difficult to solve using traditional optimization methods and approaches. Despite the importance of APP which forms the basis for the formulation for all other schedules and materials management, the results of the APP optimization are far from perfect, leaving way to major improvements.

This paper uses Genetic Algorithm (GA), and presents an optimization approach to APP modeling, which permits the search for an optimum, while considering, simultaneously, a large number of constraints of contradictory nature. A realistic case study illustrates the model and the development of the GA to an APP problem with the conditions found in an industrial context is presented.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The APP problem considering minimum changes in workforce level as well as inventory and backorders minimization simultaneously was solved for an 8-period planning horizon [3]. In 1998, the APP problem was solved using Mixed Integer Programming and considering different optimization criteria, including revenue maximization as well as inventory, backorder and set-up cost minimization [4]. Baykasoglu added further constraints to the previous models such as subcontractor selection and set-up decisions [5].

Later on, a number of artificial intelligence approaches, alone or combined with mathematical programming models have been used to solve the production planning problems

considering more constraints. GA, fuzzy logic and stochastic programming have been among the most popular ones. Among all, Wang and Fang proposed a fuzzy programming model to imitate the human decision procedure for production planning ended with a family of inexact solutions within an acceptable level [6]. A fuzzy multi-objective linear programming model for solving the multi-product APP decision problem in a fuzzy environment considering inventory level, labor levels, capacity, warehouse space and the time value of money is presented in [7]. A model to optimize the multi-site APP problem by considering a wider range of constraints describing a two-stage stochastic programming model [8].

However, little attention has been given to develop a strategy taking into account the many constraints and their combination, as they appear in practice. The combination of factors simultaneously affecting the quality of the APP is a characteristic of real-life problems and their consideration can make the difference between a purely academic treatment of the subject and a result that can be applied or transferred immediately in practice.

In this paper, a complex and realistic mathematical model is built and a GA is developed for its optimization. It goes beyond developing heuristics to solve simple strategies to optimize the APP. Instead, the approach is general, all optimization constraints are implemented into the Fitness Function and a penalty is incurred for any suboptimal solution. The model contains a large number of practical constraints including production cost, labor cost, hiring and laying off costs, holding costs (carrying inventory during plan period) and subcontracting costs.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In developing the methodology for modeling and optimizing the APP a number of strategies can be and were considered:

Strategy 1: fill the requirements using overtime – workers (all or them or only veteran personnel – workers with at least one week stage in the company) are used to work for an integer number of hours. In this case the inventory and contracting out the units to be delivered are underutilized/disregarded;

Strategy 2: fill the un-met requirements using external contractors – is a lean, outsourcing strategy in regards to keeping inventory, reducing, at the same time the workforce available to a minimum;

Strategy 3: fill requirements using up to the equivalent of a given number of weeks output in inventory, by minimizing at the same time the variation of workforce. This strategy can also minimize the use of contractors, taking advantage properties of keeping inventory to increase or keep a service level [9].

Other strategies or any linear combinations of strategies can be developed and the results of their application assessed. These strategies can be implemented as heuristics in

algorithms to optimize the planning process. However, any of these strategies is likely to produce desired results – i.e. minimum costs - only for a narrow combination of conditions and input values, which might appear briefly, as windows - during the planning horizon. The use of any set strategy would, in this case, be suboptimal in the rest of the planning horizon.

Also, it became obvious that, by using a set strategy, there would be a set relation between a number of variables (see next section) e.g. production plan in a period, number of veteran and new workers, the production, hours worked, inventory each day and cumulative inventory and the respective costs.

After examining the results of implementing the strategies presented above, it emerged that a better approach would be to avoid constraining the planning to just one of these strategies. The independent variables in this case are chosen as the number of workers each planning period and the number of hours worked, with all production and inventory levels derived from this. The only constraint imposed is the maximum level of inventory, which is a sensible condition in practice.

It was decided to use the evolutionary character of GA to determine an optimum result by exploring the whole search space. This is the equivalent of finding the best strategy or combinations of strategies at any point in time, and varying it, as necessary, to produce an optimum result. When choosing GA for the optimization process, an important element was their capacity to implement any cost function [10].

IV. MODELING OF THE APP PROBLEM

As a realistic model is sought for the APP problem, a complex combination of conditions is applied. The list of variables is by no means exhaustive, but it incorporates many decisions variables, economies of scale, hard constraints and costs, etc.

A. Variables:

Planning data:

T - Planning horizon;

D_Y - Total forecasted demand in year (units/year);

t - Each period of time in the planning horizon – granularity of the model;

N_w - Normal working time per week for the company (h);

D_{Pt} - Forecasted demand for each period in the planning horizon (units/t);

$D_{P_{tmin}}$ - The minimum forecasted demand for each period in D_Y (units/t);

$D_{P_{tmax}}$ - The maximum forecasted demand for each period in D_Y (units/t);

P_t - Production of current week (units/week);

Labor costs:

C_{RL} - Regular wage – including overheads (\$/h)

C_{OL} - Overtime wage – including overheads (\$/h)

T_L - Normal working time per worker per shift

P_L - Productivity of a veteran worker (units/h)

P_{NL} - productivity of a new worker in first week (units/h)

L_t - number of full-time permanent labors in period t - variable;

Personnel policy:

C_H - The cost of hiring one labor (\$ / Labor)

C_L - The cost of laying off one labor (\$ / Labor)

Plant running costs:

N - Actual hours company works per week - variable;

C_P - Plant running cost per hour - normal hours (\$/h)

C_{PO} - Plant running cost per hour - overtime (\$/h)

Inventory policy:

I_t - inventory level;

C_I - inventory cost to hold a single unit of product at the end of each period (\$ / unit - period);

C_S - shortage cost per unit associated with subcontracting (\$/unit);

B. Constraints

The assumptions listed below are implemented as a list of feasibility constraints. Violating any of these constraints would produce an infeasible solution:

1. The company works at least N_w hours each week;
2. The number of hours worked in a week is integer;
3. A worker will only produce an integer number of units per week. If the worker cannot produce a whole unit, he/she will be reassigned during that time for maintenance work (paid - equivalent cost for the time worked - but no direct output is obtained);
4. The company has to deliver all products corresponding to the demand each week (service level 100%);
5. The company uses the products made/kept/contracted out to satisfy demand in the following order:
 - A. units made that week by the workforce;
 - B. the shortage will be covered, if possible, from inventory;
 - C. if the company is still short of units, they will be outsourced to contractors;
6. All excess products will be stored in inventory;
7. In the first week of the planning horizon, the company has a number of workers and a number of items in storage in inventory equal with the average number of workers per week to fulfill average demand and the equivalent of an average week of production, respectively;
8. The capacity of the warehouse storing the inventory is maximum three times the average weekly output;

The assumptions above, very realistic in any manufacturing context, have also the potential to significantly simplify the modeling of the problem and the implementation of the algorithm.

It is important to point out that assumption 5 in combination with assumption 8, in fact, guide the decisions regarding the make-or-buy of products or, on the other hand, rely on your work force or adopt a very flexible hire-or-fire policy for employed personnel. As it is set, it tends to favor the existing workforce, with contracting out used only as a last resort. However, this set of assumptions can be modified to be aligned with the management's general strategies and the company's external context.

V. CHROMOSOME ENCODING

The chromosome encoding is presented with relation to the case study below. The chromosomes encode the solutions of the problem, in this case assembling the independent variables of the problem - namely the number of workers employed and the number of hours worked each period. The planning horizon was chosen 1 year with a granularity of the model of 1 week. This implies the chromosome is an array of 52×2 variables (104 independent variables).

The chromosome is illustrated in Fig. 1 part A, in a vertical format for space-saving purposes. For reference, the number of the week is displayed at the left of the chromosome. The number of hours worked is minimum 80, as explained in the previous section and set in the case study.

VI. THE GENETIC ALGORITHM

The structure of the GA is classic [10], with genetic operators adapted to the particularities of the problem. Instead of working with strings, they are tailored to work with arrays. They are illustrated in the following sections.

1. Handling Constraints

The probability to obtain an infeasible chromosome by random genetic operators (GO) is reduced as long as the operators are implemented correctly, taking into account the set of constraints detailed in Section 4. The major source of infeasibility is constraint 8. A chromosome has to be tested for feasibility after generation or application of a GO (crossover or mutation). The repair strategy proposed and tested successfully checks the level of inventory and, if constraint is not satisfied, to reduce the number of workers at the point of infeasibility (for the week when the inventory level exceeds three times the average weekly output) until the gene becomes feasible. Even if rare, it is possible to have more than one infeasible gene in a chromosome. In this case, the repair is to be done successively, from the first to the last week.

2. Crossover

The crossover is, in principle, a simple cut and swap operation. Figure 1 part B presents an example of crossover. In this example, parents P1 and P2, randomly selected from the initial operation, undergo the crossover. The cut point is randomly selected after week 13, and the two bottom-parts of the parents' genetic information are exchanged. After the operation, a feasibility check/repair is necessary.

3. Mutation

The mutation operator is, again, classic in its principle. An example of mutation operator is presented in Figure 2 part B (M1 and M2). In this example, a randomly selected chromosome of the population undergoes mutation. The genetic information from weeks 15 and 39, randomly selected, is swapped. After mutation, the chromosome has to undergo a feasibility check/repair operation.

week	Lt	N	P1	P2	C1	C2
1	228	80	268	214	268	214
2	292	81	217	269	217	269
3	158	87	352	308	352	308
4	117	86	267	317	267	317
5	170	88	377	268	377	268
6	336	81	392	350	392	350
7	333	87	224	308	224	308
8	246	82	205	207	205	207
9	215	80	328	239	328	239
10	5	82	235	297	235	297
11	42	81	360	204	360	204
12	163	87	248	376	248	376
13	238	87	372	320	372	320
14	247	89	349	330	330	349
15	73	86	374	248	248	374
16	112	80	260	204	204	260
17	53	88	344	399	399	344
18	337	83	273	243	243	273
19	215	84	221	204	204	221
20	224	83	355	359	359	355
21	76	81	271	342	342	271
22	255	80	336	313	313	336
23	277	86	398	321	321	398
24	116	85	259	298	298	259
25	4	87	260	278	278	260
26	173	84	254	283	283	254
27	129	88	241	321	321	241
28	159	80	387	381	381	387
29	291	85	332	260	260	332
30	288	80	247	246	246	247
31	134	85	228	266	266	228
32	132	85	340	310	310	340
33	27	82	264	256	256	264
34	292	88	363	274	274	363
35	39	85	285	226	226	285
36	309	80	202	260	260	202
37	119	82	257	344	344	257
38	254	86	321	266	266	321
39	379	87	320	239	239	320
40	223	83	244	329	329	244
41	236	83	355	270	270	355
42	379	80	340	218	218	340
43	313	84	375	346	346	375
44	21	81	212	299	299	212
45	161	86	398	230	230	398
46	371	83	227	243	243	227
47	258	88	203	263	263	203
48	217	82	242	341	341	242
49	307	86	237	328	328	237
50	295	83	218	245	245	218
51	236	84	302	320	320	302
52	158	86	338	368	368	338

Fig. 1 The chromosome and the crossover operators

week	Lt	N	M1	M2
1	228	80	229	80
2	292	81	329	80
3	158	87	393	86
4	117	86	296	89
5	170	88	361	86
6	336	81	257	86
7	333	87	216	80
8	246	82	333	87
9	215	80	399	80
10	5	82	219	87
11	42	81	250	82
12	163	87	343	89
13	238	87	374	86
14	247	89	311	88
15	73	86	398	85
16	112	80	291	84
17	53	88	305	87
18	337	83	216	88
19	215	84	393	89
20	224	83	296	84
21	76	81	297	82
22	255	80	325	86
23	277	86	320	85
24	116	85	369	81
25	4	87	221	84
26	173	84	290	83
27	129	88	248	84
28	159	80	273	83
29	291	85	388	86
30	288	80	345	89
31	134	85	240	84
32	132	85	312	84
33	27	82	233	85
34	292	88	390	80
35	39	85	211	86
36	309	80	362	82
37	119	82	260	87
38	254	86	317	89
39	379	87	222	86
40	223	83	258	82
41	236	83	378	80
42	379	80	242	81
43	313	84	400	87
44	21	81	356	87
45	161	86	380	83
46	371	83	210	88
47	258	88	258	86
48	217	82	399	87
49	307	86	356	82
50	295	83	375	88
51	236	84	247	88
52	158	86	225	80

Fig. 2 The chromosome and the mutation operator

4. Evaluation

The Fitness Function (FF) of each chromosome is dependent upon the costs associated with the application of the strategy associated with the corresponding particular solution. GA has a remarkable ability to incorporate and use almost any conceivable type of cost structure [10], [11]. The total cost (TC) for a solution/chromosome is the sum of all costs attached to operating the company for the next forecasting horizon:

$$TC = \sum_{i=1}^{52} (PC + WC + IC + SC)$$

PC - Production cost – takes into account the normal and overtime rate;

$$PC = C_p \quad \text{if } N \leq N_w;$$

$$PC = C_{p0} \quad \text{if } N \geq N_w$$

WC - Costs associated with workforce

$$WC = WC1_t + WC2_t$$

WC - made of wages (WC1) + hiring and firing costs (WC2);

$WC1 = N * L_t * C_{RL}$ if $N \leq N_w$; - normal working time
 $WC1 = L_t * N * C_{RL} + L_t * (N_w * N * CO_L)$ if $N \geq N_w$; - if overtime is needed

$WC2 = C_H * (L_t - L_{t-1})$ if $L_t \geq L_{t-1}$ - if workers hired
 $WC2 = C_L * (L_{t-1} - L_t)$ if $L_t < L_{t-1}$ - if workers fired

IC – Inventory keeping costs –only if inventory is positive;

$IC = (I_{t-1} + P_t + D_{Pt}) * C_I$ if $IC \geq 0$

$IC = (\text{Previous week inventory} + \text{Production of current week} - \text{Forecasted demand}) * \text{inventory keeping costs};$

Where

I_{t-1} – previous week's inventory – given for first week, calculated subsequently;

$P = N * L_t * P_L$ if $L_t \leq L_{t-1}$ – production by veteran workers

$P = (N * L_{t-1} * P_L) + N * (L_t - L_{t-1}) * P_{NL}$ if $L_t > L_{t-1}$ – production by veteran workers and newly hired workers.

D_{Pt} - forecasted demand for each period in the planning horizon (units/t) - given;

SC – Costs associated with subcontracting a part of production;

If IC, calculated as above is negative, it has to be covered by subcontracting:

If $IC < 0$, $SC = IC * C_S$

5. Selection

The stochastic sampling mechanism is used to select the next generation of chromosomes, associated with the Holland's proportionate selection or roulette wheel selection (Holland, 1975). Because the weighed roulette works for maximization of the fitness values and the GA in this case is designed to minimize the cost, a simple double transformation is applied: the inverse solutions' cost is multiplied with 10^{10} . After the GA has been applied, the true costs are restored, using the inverse operation – i.e. multiplying the inverse of the FF with 10^{10} [12].

VII. A CASE STUDY

A case study has been developed in conjunction with the model presented in last sections. The forecast for the next year is broken down in Table I. The case study is based on the following data and has co-evolved with the model of the APP problem:

TABLE I

WEEKLY DEMAND FOR THE PLANNING HORIZON							
Week	Demand	W	D	W	D	W	D
1	12000	14	9500	27	10500	40	10000
2	10500	15	11000	28	11000	41	10000
3	8000	16	10000	29	11000	42	9500
4	11500	17	10500	30	11500	43	8000
5	8000	18	11000	31	10500	44	10500
6	10000	19	10000	32	8500	45	10500
7	9000	20	9500	33	10500	46	8500
8	10500	21	10000	34	9500	47	11000
9	11500	22	11000	35	8500	48	9000
10	12000	23	12000	36	10000	49	8500
11	8000	24	8000	37	8000	50	8500
12	11000	25	9000	38	11500	51	11000
13	8500	26	12000	39	10000	52	10000

$T = 1$ year;

$D_Y = 520000$ units;

$t = 1$ week;

$N_w = 80$ h/week (two 8 hour shifts per day, 5 days/week);

D_{Pt} = forecasted demand for each period in the planning horizon (units/t) – in Table 1;

$D_{P_{tmin}} = 8000$ units;

$D_{P_{tmax}} = 12000$ units;

$P_r = 130$ units/h;

$C_{RL} = \$ 20$ /h;

$C_{OL} = \$ 30$ /h;

$T_L = 40$ h/week;

$P_L = 1$ unit/h;

$P_{NL} = 0.7$ unit/h;

$C_H = \$ 800$;

$C_L = \$ 1500$;

$C_p = \$ 2600$ /h;

$C_{PO} = \$3900$ /h;

$C_I = \$ 10$ per week per unit;

$C_S = \$ 80$ /unit up to 100 units/week;

$C_S = \$ 60$ /unit over 100 units/week;

The values presented above were used to develop and test the genetic operators. The cost function is implemented as a subroutine composed of the relevant cost modules. The cost structure is flexible and can be easily modified to suit any similar problem if necessary, since constraints can be varied in magnitude and other constraints can be added as required.

VIII. CONCLUSION

A complex and realistic model for the optimization of the APP has been developed. It incorporates the most important constraints and costs currently encountered in a manufacturing company.

The GA for the optimization of the APP is in an advanced implementation state. All operators have been developed and tested and will be integrated in the full algorithm shortly. Preliminary results are promising.

Further work will address the following:

- Finalization of the full GA and its testing;

- Implementation of a yet more complex cost structure, ideally by developing a framework to incorporate all realistic costs that can appear in practice;
- Optimality of results and how they are influenced by the relative level of different classes of costs on the strategy to employ, patterns of strategies as the level of costs vary;
- The possibility to address stochastic events and their influence on the optimality of the APP.

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- B. Fahimnia, R. Marian, B. Motevallian, M. Mohammad Esmail, & K. Abhary, "A heuristic method to optimize manufacturing lead time", to be published in *the 17th International DAAAM Symposium*, Austria, Vienna, 2006.
- B. Fahimnia, L. H. S. Luong, M. Mohammad Esmail, B. Motevallian, & R. Marian, "The negative impacts of globalization on local manufacturing", to be published in *the 17th International DAAAM Symposium*, Austria, Vienna, 2006.

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